

THE ROLE OF THE SUBJECT OF MUSIC CULTURE IN INSTILLING OUR NATIONAL SPIRITUALITY IN STUDENTS

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Annotation: *In this article, the heritage of Uzbek folk music, historical development, great scientists who have made a great contribution to science, literature, art and culture, thoughts directly related to culture and education, ideas about the independence of ideas and concepts, teaching the subject of music culture, education of national spirituality in the minds of students, moral and aesthetic education, thoughts about the education of morality, research scientists.*

Key words: *The subject of musical culture, science, literature, art, culture, spiritual and aesthetic education, reality, theory, historical, process, musical development.*

National revival is a very wide, deep, complex historical process that covers all spheres of life of our nation – economy, politics, spirituality, science, language history, traditions, crafts, architecture, as well as all issues directly related to human perfection.

Music also plays an important role in the development of our national spirituality. It is one of the most ancient and, at the same time, one of the spheres of national musical art, widespread in the popular masses, deeply embedded in his marriage. Music also reflects real reality. The power of music to influence our national spirituality is so great that science has already proven that it is possible to treat patients with its help.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina had attached great importance to the power of influence of music and put forward the idea that certain mental disorders could be cured by means of

musical melodies. The great philosopher Abu Nasr Farabi, in his book "Musik al-kabr", expressed his valuable views on the types of melodies of music theory, the reasons for Origin, the spiritual, spiritual influence on a person. Farobius was not only a theorist in music, but also a practitioner. He himself also gained fame as a famous musician, an excellent musician and composer, the inventor of a new musical instrument. Reflecting on the wonderful magical power, miraculous effect of music, in his work "on the origin of the sciences", Phorobius States: "this science is useful in this sense that it regulates a person who has lost his balance, perfecting and maintaining the balance of a people who have not reached perfection". In particular, in national culture, music reveals a world of high feelings, delightful ideas. Spiritually rich, pure perfection makes people.¹ The child will be able to feel the music as soon as he does not yet know how to hold a pen in his hands, read and write. Often these early impressions affect the formation of attitudes towards music. Therefore, music education was also emphasized in the main areas of reform of general education schools.

Music, first of all, softens the feelings of children. It evokes a lot of human qualities in them, such as the feeling of musical works. Of course, literature, history, sports and other fields play a big role in maturing human qualities. Consequently, nazm and music always live side by side. Nature is born under taasurots, and, moreover, forms in kindergarten and school. Music lessons educate students not only in elegance, but also in a broad sense spiritually - morally. It would be nice if our songs, statuses, which passed from generation to generation, withstood the decline of the some times and embodied the aspirations, aspirations of the people, received a wider place from the programs of all kinds of schools, pedagogical institutes. In the documents on Education adopted in the following years (concept of music education and upbringing, general educational standards, a new program in the science of music culture), the education and upbringing of music involves the widespread use of samples of Uzbek folk music, musical heritage (developed classical melodies and songs of the status type, large

¹ Abu Nasr Farabi's book " Musik al-kabr

songs, epics and musical folklore) and, in this way, it is envisaged to widely use their samples and in this way restore our ancient cultural musical values.

In the new program of the science of music culture, samples of professional music in the oral tradition, which are recommended for partial singing and mainly listening, are studied in the course of classes and extracurricular activities, in this regard, various subjects are studied in the preparation process the basis of statuses, history of uzbek music, singing or voicing, conducting, basic and additional musical instruments, he school is also used in the study of the repertoire of music, it is also used in the study.

The program of music education and education, so that the content of the same darsnig and changed dramatically, introduced new subjects that could be applied to the study of a number of national music through the unambiguous reduction of Russian and European Music. As a result of this, there were also changes in the composition, themes and usuliyot of classes.

These changes also caused several problems to arise after that, in addition to studying our national spiritual values, paving the way for the restoration of Ancient Traditions. For example, now all music teachers need to study samples of national classical, professional music and folklore. To do this, first of all, music textbooks, without music sample collections and usuliyati-specific materials on the recording for listening, it is impossible to ensure that complex music samples are mastered at the required level. The science of music culture serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of students, to carry out the upbringing of national pride and patriotism, to cultivate creative skills, sophistication and artistic taste, to expand the circle of thought, to educate independence and initiative.

The introduction of the state educational standard in musical education, among all subjects, makes it possible to make full-fledged use of national musical heritage. These were reflected in the children's mass folk songs and songs, in the creative activities of singers and musicians. Such possibilities of musical art serve as a unique and unrepeatable resource for the upbringing of a new generation, their harmonious growth.

For a long time, the education and education of Uzbek music, including the East, was improved on the example of pedagogy and its excellent methodologies, teacher and disciple traditions. Therefore, the new content of education in music culture implies the upbringing of the younger generation at the level of a civilized person who can inherit our national musical heritage, perceive the wealth of Universal Music. Choral singing is a complex psychological-physiological process. Vocal-choral work in music culture lessons, moral-aesthetic education of students is the most active form of teaching. Singing as a choir enhances the attention of students, develops memory, speech, expands the voice range, grows musical training, the period of mutation passes lightly, the worldview takes shape from year to year.

Zabardast writer of our time, world-famous writer adib Genghis Aitmatov writes in his novel "Kunda": "life, death, love, enthusiasm and inspiration all tell Music, already, we achieve the highest hurl in the medium of music, we have fought for this hurl since the times when our minds burst, throughout our history, but we have achieved it only in music".

National music teaches the perception and appreciation of the surrounding phenomena of beauty, arming with subtle taste and hur thought, expanding the spiritual world. Therefore, it was not for nothing that music was a philosophy without language. Music can soften the human soul, evoke in it Feelings of kindness and compassion, which are indicative of faith. At the same time, the content of statuses is also tasked with the artistic expression of the ideas of the doctrine of mysticism, which is in accordance with the ideology of the Great State. Naturally, the study of these complex scientific issues was entrusted to mature musicologist scientists in every possible way.¹

Thanks to national independence, music creation got rid of political-ideological repression, an opportunity for literal freedom of creativity was formed. In particular, the possibilities of extensive study of the rich spiritual heritage left by such great breeds as Abu Nasr Farabi, Abdurakhman Jami, Darvishali Changiy were limited in the Soviet period, when any nationalism was denied. From this to tashhari, until our

¹ Genghis Aitmatov " Kunda " T-2018.

independence, our compatriots could not attend the festival of Oriental music, which was regularly held in the French capital of Paris.¹

Today, the situation has completely changed. A number of international music festivals, which are taking place, are becoming a dead end in highlighting the talents of young art lovers of the Republic it is the same fact that such prestigious competitions as the international music festival "Taronas of the East", "Nihol", "voice of the future", "five initiatives " serve as an important factor in the recognition of young talents to the world.

It is not for nothing that "shashmakom" is credited with the fact that the delivery of the great masterpiece to the future generation depends precisely on today's artists, musicians and singers. After all, it is a dangerous situation that some young "artists" today are promoting Harb's talotop music, thereby creating a gap in the spiritual world of young people. However, research carried out by researchers in the United States of America once again proves that music, which is part of the East, hususan, "Shashmakom", is one of the factors leading people to goodness.

The fact is that an interesting study was carried out in one of the large maternity homes. According to him, in the rooms where the baby and mothers lay, they initially heard classical melodies, which took place from the "Shashmakom". As a result, mothers have a good mood, increased affection for their babies, babies are also relaxed, relaxed, most noticeably, mothers have increased affection for their children, and even breast milk has increased.

After a certain time in the same rooms there were again sounds of music, only this time Harb's music, rich in noise, consisting of shouts, was broadcast. The result was as the researchers expected, that is, the condition of mothers and babies changed in a negative way, their nerves were impaired, and even the state of stay of Mothers ' Milk was observed. Examples of this are quite numerous. It is necessary for us to perceive such manifestations as an infectious disease, unknown to us from a moral nature, alien to our national values and views, but currently penetrating into our lives.

¹ S.Yudasheva. Development of music education and education in Uzbekistan. Textbook, Tashkent, publishing house "teacher", 1985

In fact, it is becoming more obvious how a huge factor in musical education is in the upbringing of a perfect person. Therefore, we should try to make the growing younger generation explore our rich musical heritage, escape from light-elpy, blunt tones and raise the artistic taste, musical culture of ULR, expand its spiritual world. In this regard, in addition to the unique masterpieces of our national heritage, such as "Shashmakom", we need to teach and explain in a timely manner the masterpieces of such great composers as Mozart, Beethoven, Bach, Tchaikovsky, Rachmaninoff, Khachaturian, whom jaxon recognized. We are today's descendants of the Great Homeland, which from time immemorial threw the whole world with its wisdom.

Therefore, it is necessary to preserve our great monuments, cultural and spiritual heritage, to fully use the rarest masterpieces of musical art in the upbringing of a perfect person.

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